

Energy-Classical Frequency in Quantum Oscillator Part IV

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In Part III we argued that a Schrodinger equation of the form: $a \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + bxx W(x) = E W(x)$ may be scaled $x \rightarrow y$ such that $yy = xx \sqrt{ba}$ and $E \rightarrow E \sqrt{a/b}$ so that E is proportional to $\sqrt{b/a}$. We applied this idea to the quantum oscillator and noted that classically w , the angular frequency, for the same equation is $\sqrt{b/a}$. We further argued that this implies the momentum operator in quantum mechanics should scale as $1/x$ as d/dx does.

In this note we use a slightly different argument to analyze this same problem. Instead of treating the classical oscillator and time-independent Schrodinger equation as separate, we link them and show that scaling must occur with E being proportional to w . Furthermore we argue that if quantum mechanically one wishes to use probabilities $f(p,x)$ to calculate average kinetic energy at x i.e. $KE(at x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ f(p,x) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ f(p,x) \}$, then $f(p,x) = f(px)$ and pp should scale as $1/x$. Thus comparison of the classical oscillator equation directly with a statistical average type of quantum equation which uses $V(x)$, E and $KE(at x)$ yields information about E , $f(p,x)$ and p i.e. introduces the idea of wavelength. Furthermore the discrete quantum energy values $E = \hbar w (n+.5)$ are dependent on w not through any boundary value considerations.

Classical Oscillator

Newton's conservation of energy equation for an oscillator is:

$$p^2/2m + .5kx^2 = E \quad \text{where } E = \frac{1}{2} kAA, A = \text{amplitude} \quad ((1))$$

Thus A may take on any value within reason. Due to the symmetry of ((1)) this is of the form of a Pythagoreas' equation (or dot product) (as noted in Part I) and one may have scaling i.e.

$$p^2/(2mE) + .5kx^2/E = 1 \quad ((2))$$

This suggests that the first two terms on the LHS should be $\cos(wt)\cos(wt)$ and $\sin(wt)\sin(wt)$. With $x = A\sin(wt)$ and $v = dx/dt$ one finds that $w = \sqrt{k/m}$ and so there is a distinct frequency in the problem even though E may take on any value.

Quantum Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

The time-independent Schrodinger equation for an oscillator is:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + .5kx^2 W(x) = E_n W(x) \quad ((3))$$

This equation, as argued on previous occasions, is closely linked to the classical one ((1)) if one divides by $W(x)$. In such a case:

$$KE(at x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W = KE classical(x) \quad ((4))$$

In particular, the link between the time-independent Schrodinger equation and the classical conservation of energy equation holds for any $V(x)$ and any energy level.

Given the nature of the Schrodinger equation ((3)) which mathematically is an eigenvalue equation, discrete E values emerge which are dependent on the boundary conditions applied to $W(x)$.

In fact, the discreteness of E is often thought of as due to the boundary conditions.

Here we argue that the comparison of ((3)) with the classical periodic oscillator energy equation may shed light on the quantum system. As in ((2)) we divide both sides of ((3)) by E which is no longer $.5kAA$. Nevertheless, the kinetic energy and potential energy terms must map into $\cos(wt)\cos(wt)$, $\sin(wt)\sin(wt)$ in the sense that they must have the same coefficients, in fact these coefficients must be absorbed into x so the coefficients become 1. In other words, the quantum time-dependent Schrodinger equation takes on a similar form as $\cos(wt)\cos(wt) + \sin(wt)\sin(wt) = 1$ which shows periodicity even though there is no time in the time-independent Schrodinger equation. This implies that:

$$.5kxx / E = yy \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \{ d/dx dW/dx / W \} 1/2m 1/E = d/dy dW/dy / W \quad ((5b))$$

If $x \rightarrow y$ such that $yy = .5 \sqrt{(km)} xx$, then both kinetic and potential energy are strictly functions of y - all parameters have disappeared as must be the case if the two energy terms are to mimic $\cos(wt)\cos(wt)$ and $\sin(wt)\sin(wt)$. This occurs because the momentum operator is of the form $-id/dx$. E then becomes proportional to $w = \sqrt{k/m}$ implying that the classical angular frequency is a key part of quantum energy. Even though the quantum Schrodinger equation only contains t through $W(x,t) = W(x)\exp(-iEnt)$, the equation maps to the classical one as shown above and so the classical Pythagorea's form also applies to the quantum equation and forces it to be linked to w even though the quantum particle is not followed in time.

Generalized Quantum Schrodinger Equation

In the above section we considered the explicit time-independent Schrodinger equation ((3)). What happens if one considers a more general statistical energy conservation equation and links it to the oscillator? We suggest:

$$KE(at x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \quad pp/2m f(p,x) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \quad f(p,x) \} \quad ((6))$$

Comparison with the oscillator suggests that p must be of the form of $1/\text{length}$ and that $f(p,x) = f(px)$ so that a variable change may occur in x as it occurs in $.5kxx$. This already brings in the notion of momentum as linked to $1/\text{wavelength}$ so that kinetic energy scales as $1/xx$. This is identical to the idea $f(p,x) = f(px)$ where px suggests scaling of x by p or a special length proportional to $1/p$ such that $p * 1/p$ is the same for all p . As noted in Part I this leads to an oscillator E_n proportional to w such that for $-Et$, t proportional to $1/w$ means that $E/w = \text{constant}$ for all w i.e. all different springs.

In short, without knowing the form of quantum mechanics as a statistical theory in x (without t) for the time-independent case, we argue that one may surmise information about p as $1/\text{wavelength}$ and probability as a being a function of px by comparing with a periodic classical energy conservation equation.

Conclusion

One may compare the time-independent Schrodinger equation directly to the classical energy conservation equation for any potential and any energy level. In the case of the oscillator, this means that the classical form $\cos(\omega t)\cos(\omega t) + \sin(\omega t)\sin(\omega t) = 1$ which follows from the conservation of energy equation must also apply to the time-independent Schrodinger equation even though E is not $.5kAA$ for all A in the quantum case. Thus dividing the RHS of the time-independent Schrodinger equation by $EW(x)$ and forcing the two terms on the LHS (KE and PE) to be parameter independent to mimic $\cos(\omega t)\cos(\omega t)$ and $\sin(\omega t)\sin(\omega t)$ leads to scaling of x such that $x \rightarrow y$ where $yy = .5\sqrt{k/m}$. This is due to the $1/x^2$ form of kinetic energy and the insistence that the quantum equation mimic the form of the classical periodic one even though quantum mechanics does not follow a particle in time while the classical does. This forces $E(\text{quantum})$ to be proportional to ω , angular frequency, which is a strictly classical concept.

We also consider the general case of $KE(\text{at } x) \text{ quantum} = \{\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ f(p,x)\} / \{\text{Sum over } p \ f(p,x)\}$. Comparison with the classical oscillator suggests that p goes as $1/\text{length}$ i.e. there is a wavelength in the problem and that $f(p,x) = f(px)$ such that scaling may occur. Thus we argue that a comparison with a classical periodic system may reveal important features of quantum mechanical behaviour, namely the form px in $f(px)$ which in other notes we have assigned to the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$.